

Fig. 2. Plot of $F_j([X])$ vs C_x for thallium(I)-1-naphthaleneacetate system in

- (a) 10% Ethanol at 25° (—○—○—)
- (b) 50% Ethanol at 25° (—□—□—)
- (c) 10% Ethanol at 15° (—△—△—)

Fig. 3. Plot of percentage distribution of thallium in various forms vs $-\log C_x$ at 25°

- (a) Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in aqueous medium (—○—○—)
- (b) Thallium(I)-3-indoleacetate in 10% ethanol (—△—△—)
- (c) Thallium(I)-3-indolebutyrate in 10% ethanol (—□—□—)

Percentage distribution of thallium in various forms as a function of ligand concentration is calculated and the values are presented in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig. 4. Plot of percentage distribution of thallium in various forms vs $-\log C_x$ for thallium(I)-1-naphthalene in

- (a) 10% Ethanol at 25° (—○—○—)
- (b) 50% Ethanol at 25° (—△—△—)
- (c) 10% Ethanol at 15° (—□—□—)

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some New 4-Ylidenetetronic Acid Derivatives*

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THE tetronic acid ring system constitutes important structural features in a wide range of biologically important natural products e.g., vitamin C and cardenolide digitoxigenin. The ring system is a characteristic structural feature in the 'pulvinic

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acid³ group found in lichens¹. The 4-ylidenetetrone acids variabilin, strobilin and tetrenolin, were shown to have strong antibiotic activity¹. Various pulvinic acid analogues (4-ylidenetetrone acid derivatives) have been synthesised and many have been shown to possess useful anti-inflammatory properties². A number of nitrogen containing pulvinic acid lichen metabolites are known; pulvinamide, epanorin and rhizocarpic acid are amides formally derived from combination of pulvinic acid with ammonia, L-leucine and L-phenylalanine, respectively³.

In the present paper the synthesis of a variety of nitrogen containing 4-ylidenetetrone acid derivatives are reported. Pulvinic dilactone (I) (a lichen metabolite) is prepared according to Sutton *et al.*⁴. It was condensed with equimolar amounts of various natural amino acids viz., glycine, β -alanine, α -alanine, aspartic acid, tyrosine, tryptophan, glutamic acid, lysine, histidine and also with dapson (a leprostatic drug). This resulted in the cleavage of one of the lactonic rings to give the respective amide derivatives, while the other lactonic ring of pulvinic dilactone remained intact. These derivatives (II) gave positive FeCl_3 test indicating the presence of enolic hydroxyl group. They closely resembled epanorin and rhizocarpic acid (isolated from lichens *Epanora lecanora* and *Rhizocarpon geographicum*, respectively) and hence are their analogues. The above 4-ylidenetetrone acid derivatives, when crystallised from ethanol, underwent ethanolysis to give respective ethyl ethers (III), which did not respond to FeCl_3 test due to lack of enolic hydroxy group. The ethanolysis took place because of the highly reactive enolic hydroxyl which was subsequently etherified. Pulvinic dilactone when condensed with dapson (1 : 1) in acetic acid medium gave (IV). The products have been adequately characterised by means of elemental analysis, uv, ir, nmr and mass spectral data. The nmr spectrum of compound (IIa) showed signals at (δ values) : 3.9(d, CH_2), 6.8(broad, NH) and 7.5(m, aromatic hydrogens). Its ethyl ether (IIIa) has additional magnetic resonances at 3.5 (q, CH_2) and 2.5(t, CH_3). Mass spectrum of compound (IIa) has M^+ 333 with fragments at 89, 117, 145, 178, 234, 264 and 290 (m/z values) which are

characteristic of pulvinic series⁵. The compounds (IIa-IIIi) have the absorption maxima at 221, 288 and 372 nm (methanol) while the dapson derivative (IV) at 221, 272 and 290 nm (methanol). The ir and uv data are closely related to those of rhizocarpic acid and epanorin⁶.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. UV is recorded on a Shimadzu MPS-5000 and pmr is recorded on Varian A60D instrument in CDCl_3 , using TMS as internal standard. Mass spectral studies were carried out on a Varian Mat-CH-7 mass spectrophotometer.

4-Ylidenetetrone acid derivatives (IIa-IIIi) : A mixture of pulvinic dilactone (0.01 mole) and amino acid (0.01 mole) in 15 ml glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the separated solid was filtered and washed with petroleum ether (60-80°). IR : 3360 broad (OH, NH), 1760 broad (C=O), 1610 m (aliphatic C=C), 1550s (NH), 1410w, 1360w, 1330w, 1185s and 700s (aromatic rings) cm^{-1} .

Ethyl ethers of IIa-IIIi : IIa (0.01 mole) was refluxed in ethanol (10 ml) for 10 min and cooled. The separated yellow compound was filtered as needles (IIIa). IR : 1764s (lactonic carbonyl), 1670m (amide carbonyl), 1090m, 1065 and 1030w (all for C-O-C) cm^{-1} .

4-Ylidenetetrone acid derivative of dapson (IV) : A mixture of pulvinic dilactone (0.01 mole) and dapson (0.01 mole) in 15 ml glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 5 hr. The reaction mixture is cooled and the acetic acid is removed under vacuum. The separated gum is triturated in methanol to give dark yellow derivative. It is crystallised from acetic acid as shining crystals. IR : 3340 broad (OH, NH), 1765 broad (C=O), 1665m (amide carbonyl), 1585s (aromatic C=C), 1320s, 1305w and 1160s (sulfone) cm^{-1} .

Biological screening results : All the compounds reported in Table I were tested *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity by cup-plate method⁷ and antifungal activity by food poisoning method⁸. The bacteria employed were *Bacillus pumilus* and *Sarcina lutea* (gram +ve) and *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas ovalis* (gram -ve) and the fungi were *Drechslera rostrata* and *Fusarium oxysporum*.

The antibacterial tests were carried at the concentration of 1 mg/ml, and 0.05 ml solution was placed in each cup. All the 4-ylidenetetrone acid derivatives showed antibacterial activity, IIb, IIIi and IIIh being more active against the above bacteria than the rest of the compounds. Compounds IIc and IIg were relatively more active against *B. pumilus* and *S. lutea* but were moderately active against *P. vulgaris* and *P. ovalis*.

All the compounds showed moderate fungicidal activity at 100 ppm. However, they showed

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS OF 4-YLIDENETETRONIC ACID DERIVATIVES

Sl. No.	Compound	R	Yield %	Solvent for crystallisation	m.p. °C	%N	
						Found	(Calcd.)
1	IIa	glycine	75	acetic acid	214	3.83 (3.84)	
2	IIb	β -alanine	65	chloroform	182	3.71 (3.69)	
3	IIc	α -alanine	70	chloroform	202	3.68 (3.69)	
4	IId	aspartic acid	72	acetic acid	186	2.77 (2.76)	
5	IIe	tyrosine	65	aqueous ethanol	189	3.12 (3.08)	
6	IIf	tryptophan	70	aqueous ethanol	178	5.64 (5.67)	
7	IIg	glutamic acid	65	chloroform	206	3.15 (3.18)	
8	IIh	lysine	70	chloroform	126	6.39 (6.42)	
9	III	histidine	75	acetic acid	112	9.39 (9.43)	
10	IIIa	glycine	75	ethanol	203	3.53 (3.56)	
11	IV		70	methanol/acetic acid	238	5.19 (5.20)	

enhanced activity at a higher concentration of 300 ppm. IId was found to have total inhibition in both the concentrations. Compounds IIa, IIe, IIf and IV were relatively more toxic to *D. rostrata* and less toxic to *F. oxysporum*. Compounds IIb and IIc were more active against *F. oxysporum* but were moderately toxic to *D. rostrata*.

Compounds IIa-IIc and IV were studied for their anti-inflammatory activity up to 200 mg/kg following oral administration in mice and was found to have no activity.

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Polyphenolic Constituents of *Magnolia pterocarpa* Roxb.

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MAGNOLIA pterocarpa Roxb. (Fam: Magnoliaceae) is a lofty evergreen tree growing in tropical Himalayan forests, Assam, Khasia Hills and Chittagong, upto an altitude of 3000 ft¹. There is no report of previous work on this plant although the genus *Magnolia* is wellknown for producing extractives of diverse patterns such as sesquiterpenoids, lignans and alkaloids of benzylisoquinoline, bis-benzylisoquinoline, aporphine and oxoaporphine types. The present paper describes the isolation and characterisation of three tetrahydrofurofuranoid lignans viz., (+)-sesamin (I) (yield 0.025%), (-)-eudesmin (II) (yield 0.028%) (+)-fargesin (III) (yield 0.003%) and one furocoumarin, imperatorin (IV) (yield 0.003%), along with dimethyl terephthalate (yield 0.001%) and β -sitosterol (yield 0.007%) from the leaves of *M. pterocarpa*. To our knowledge, the present isolation of imperatorin constitutes the first report on the occurrence of a coumarin in the family Magnoliaceae, which makes a new addition to the existing list of families elaborating coumarins.

Air dried and powdered leaves (700 g) of *M. pterocarpa* was Soxhletted with light petrol (60-80°) and chloroform in succession for 40 hr each. The residue from the light petrol extract was chromatographed over silica gel, elution being carried out